

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring

Authors:

Petr Kolář, Zuzana Jechumtálová (GFU)

April 2024

CONTENTS

1 INTRODUCTION	3
2 HISTORICAL SEISMICITY	4
2.1 Historical felt seismicity.....	4
2.2 Historical tectonic events	9
2.3 Summation of historical seismicity.....	13
3 SEISMIC MONITORING ARRAY	14
4 SEISMIC MONITORING DATA PROCESSING	17
4.1 Data processing	17
4.2 Observed seismic events in the vicinity of CO ₂ storage site	18
4.3 Step-Rate-Test monitoring	21
5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	24
5.1 Summary	24
5.2 Possible configurations of seismic network.....	25
6 TECHNICAL NOTES	26
6.1 Seismic station deployment	26
6.2 Possibly expected scientific results	26
REFERENCES	27
APPENDICES	28
Appendix 1: Catalogue tectonic events	28
Appendix 2: Recorded seismic events.....	32

1 INTRODUCTION

The main goal of WP1 is to obtain suitable data for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site. These data sources will be used as inputs during the development of a three-dimensional static geological model of the storage site and complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and mainly monitoring (WP7), including seismic monitoring and catalogue of earthquakes macroseismically felt in the site Zar-3 and/or in its vicinity.

Institute of Geophysics (GFU) is a leading Czech research institute in the area of seismology, studying seismic source processes of both natural and induced earthquakes. Monitoring of a CO₂ storage site will represent a new application opportunity in GFU seismological research portfolio. From scientific point of view, CO₂ storage deployment has similar features with the problems that arise during hydraulic fracturing and geothermal energy production. Some theoretical aspects of these activities have been studied in GFU for a decade: e.g. changes in seismic regime in affected regions, magnitudes and mechanism of induced events, changes of stress regime in the region, etc.

Seismicity is one of the basic data for the description and assessment of the planned storage complex and surrounding areas according to the CO₂ Storage Act (85/2012 Sb.) and the EU Directive 2009/31/EC. These regulations only specify the parameters (quantities) to be monitored, not the monitoring methods; these are chosen by each operator according to the rule "...shall be based on the best practice...".

The 2011 EU Directive Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide, Guidance Document 2, Characterization of the Storage Complex, CO₂ Stream Composition, Monitoring and Corrective Measures, again mentions the seismicity as one of the data for the characterization of the CO₂ storage site, while stressing the importance of knowing the seismicity for the "baseline characterization" based on known earthquake data. The need for knowledge of induced seismicity is also mentioned, without defining how to obtain such knowledge, but our network of local seismic stations is the proper access.

2 HISTORICAL SEISMICITY

This chapter describes known historical earthquakes which excited macroseismic effect in Zar-3 site (or in its vicinity) for the purposes of investigation potential CO₂ storage in this area. The chapter combines two standard approaches: (i) historical earthquakes with known macroseismic effect and (ii) recorded tectonic events, which were located in the vicinity of the area. The chapter is based on data from macroseismic archive of Institute of Geophysics and on seismic bulletins

2.1 Historical felt seismicity

Macroseismic observations of the effects of felt earthquakes are important to assess historical seismicity. At a time when seismic instruments were not used to record ground motion this was the only source of information on seismicity. Based on description how inhabitants felt the earthquake and what kinds of effects they observed on their nearby environment (objects movements, damages of furniture, buildings, etc.) the intensity of earthquake could be determined. The magnitude of historical earthquakes can be estimated using such intensity in the epicenter.

By gathering of historical observations, the size of maximum ground motions could be assessed at the site of our interest in the past. The first macroseismic observation in the Czech Republic is dated in the 10th century. The observations from the distance up to 30 km from the CO₂ storage site Zar-3 will be discussed.

26 strong earthquakes (Tab. 2-1, Figs. 2-1 and 2-2) have been felt in the vicinity of storage site Zar-3 up to now. Majority of these events were located in Austria, four in the Czech Republic, two in Slovakia and one from Italy, Montenegro, Romania, Slovenia and Croatia.

Tab. 2-1: Earthquakes felt in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Zar-3 up to now

Epicentrum	Origin time [UTC]	Lat [°]	Lon [°]	Depth [km]	Mag
A - Vienna Basin	1837-03-14 15:40	47.5	15.5	5-59	
SK - Žilina	1858-01-15 19:15	49.2	18.8	5-59	
A - Vienna Basin	1876-07-17 12:17	48	15.2	5-59	
SK - Dobrá Voda	1906-01-10 01:06	48.6	17.5	1-4	3.7
CZ - Velká Bíteš	1916-12-12 22:15	49.3	16.2		
A - Vienna Basin	1938-11-08 03:11:34	48	16.5	35	5.2
A - Vienna Basin	1939-09-18 00:14:31	47.6	16		5.1
A - Vienna Basin	1963-12-02 06:49:05	48.03	16.2	0	4.8
A - Vienna Basin	1964-10-27 19:46:11	47.782	15.963	10.2	4.4
A - Vienna Basin	1972-04-16 10:10:05.96	47.811	16.099	11.4	4.8

IT - Friuli	1976-05-06 20:00:13.97	46.313	13.294	13.4	6
CZ - Ostrava-Orlová	1977-03-24 03:31:23	49.87	18.48	0	
Černá Hora - Bar	1979-04-15 06:19:44.03	42.037	19.225	9	6.2
CZ - Náchod	1979-11-21 18:57:29.00	50.380	16.170	33	2.6
A - Mariazell	1983-04-14 14:52:14.47	47.702	15.047	10.7	4.5
ROM - Vrancea	1986-08-30 21:28:37.05	45.575	26.396	137.4	6.5
CZ – Jeseníky	1986-09-10 23:17:48.90	50.067	17.156	10	3.8
SLO - Bovec	1998-04-12 10:55:36.35	46.213	13.601	24.5	5.3
A - Vienna Basin	2000-07-11 02:49:47.80	48.010	16.440	12	4.2
A - Vienna Basin	2000-07-11 10:56:03.00	47.990	16.320	1	3.9
A - Vienna Basin	2013-09-20 02:06:34.10	47.96	16.39	17	4.3
A - Vienna Basin	2016-04-25 10:28:22.74	48.092	16.037	12.2	4.1
HR - Zagreb	2020-12-29 11:19:54.88	45.423	16.220	10.1	6.4
A - Vienna Basin	2021-01-20 07:30:27.08	47.570	14.386	10	4.1
A - Vienna Basin	2021-03-30 16:25:01.00	47.773	16.184	7	4.6
A - Neunkirchen	2021-04-19 22:57:11.00	47.745	16.194	8	4.5

Fig. 2-1: Map with earthquakes felt in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Zar-3.

Fig. 2-2: Zoomed map with earthquakes felt in the vicinity of Zar-3 storage site

There are 263 macroseismic observations in the archive of Institute of Geophysics. The observation density is proportional to the population density at a given place and time.

For each listed earthquake, the macroseismic intensity in specific municipality is given. A map of observation sites – municipalities is displayed in Fig. 2-3; the list of all the events is in an Appendix 1.

Fig. 2-3: Map with macroseismic observations in the vicinity of Zar-3 storage site.

For important constructions such as CO₂ storages, it is necessary to assess the peak ground acceleration (PGA) in the site. PGA is equal to the maximum ground acceleration that occurred during earthquake shaking at a location. It is equal to the amplitude of the largest absolute acceleration recorded on an accelerogram at a site during a particular earthquake. PGA is often split into the horizontal and vertical components, because horizontal PGAs are generally larger. Sometimes the value of peak ground velocity (PGV) is also given. However, PGA is more important parameter than PGV for earthquake engineering.

It is possible to refer the Intensity to peak horizontal amplitude (PHA) (as in Tab. 2-2) to see perceived shaking and potential damages. Based on this relation the peak horizontal ground acceleration in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Zar-3 did not achieve 0.1 g in the past.

Tab. 2-2: Relation between ground motion parameters, instrumental intensity, and potential damages resulting from an earthquake (Wald et al., 1999)

Intensity	PHA [g]	PGV [cm/s]	perceived shaking	potential damage
I	< 0.0017	< 0.1	not felt	none
II-III	0.0017 – 0.014	0.1 – 1.1	weak	none

IV	0.014 – 0.039	1.1 – 3.4	light	none
V	0.039 – 0.092	3.4 – 8.1	moderate	very light
VI	0.092 – 0.18	8.1 – 16	strong	light
VII	0.18 – 0.34	16 – 31	very strong	moderate
VIII	0.34 – 0.65	31 – 60	severe	moderate to heavy
IX	0.65 – 1.24	60 – 116	violent	heavy
X+	> 1.24	> 116	extreme	very heavy

2.2 Historical tectonic events

Czech Regional Seismic Network (CRSN) monitors earthquakes and other seismic events (like rock bursts and explosions in mines) in the Czech Republic. Recently, the regional network consists of twenty permanent broadband stations situated in the territory of the Czech Republic, the CRSN is operated by three institutions. Institute of Geophysics CAS operates twelve stations Průhonice (PRU), Kašperské Hory (KHC), Nový Kostel (NKC), Hora Svaté Kateřiny (HSKC), Dobruška/Polom (DPC), Úpice (UPC), Panská Ves (PVCC), Zvíkov (ZVC), Přimda (PRIC), Třešť (TREC), Králíky (KRLC), Ostrava-Krásné Pole (OKC), Institute of Rock Structure and Mechanics CAS three stations Chvaleč (CHVC), Ostaš (OSTC), Český Krumlov (CKRC) and Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno five stations Vranov (VRAC), Moravský Beroun (MORC), Moravský Krumlov (KRUC), Velká Javorina (JAVC), Stádkov (STAC).

There are digital bulletins of tectonic events since 1976. Before seismic stations were used mainly to detect big earthquakes and underground nuclear explosions. The network of seismic stations was not dense and the completeness of the catalogs was beyond magnitude 3. There was no station in South Moravia region. The increased level of microseismicity, found after the installation of the first digital stations in the wider region (1983-1987) and especially after the construction of the first permanent stations at Moravský Krumlov and Velká Javorina in 1993, led to the gradual expansion and modernization of the monitoring infrastructure in this area.

The local network of seismic stations MONET (operated by Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno) is used to monitor the seismic activity of the North Moravia, which is characterized by stronger historical earthquakes, regionally anomalous levels of microseismicity and other manifestations of increased geodynamic activity (Nysa-Morava zone). In South Moravia region, a local monitoring network of the Dukovany nuclear power plant EDU (operated by Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno) is used to detect weaker seismic events.

The Tab. 2-3 summarizes the parameters of stations that can be used to detect and locate seismic events from our area of interest. In the 1990s, there were only three stations KRUC, JAVC and VRAC, but in the period 2013-2015, another eight stations were added (Fig. 2-4).

Tab. 2-3: Seismic stations in the surroundings of CO₂ storage site

Operated since	Station	Place	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Operated by
27.9.1993	KRUC	Moravský Krumlov	49.0619	16.3952	IPE
27.9.1993	JAVC	Velká Javořina	48.8591	17.6707	IPE
4.11.1993	VRAC	Vranov	49.3084	16.5933	IPE
13.11.2013	MYDU	Myslivořice	49.1210	15.9501	IPE-EDU
31.1.2014	NADU	Naloučany	49.2441	16.1270	IPE-EDU
14.8.2014	RUDU	Rudlice	48.9411	16.0568	IPE-EDU
9.9.2014	SEDU	Štěpánovský lom	48.9570	16.3306	IPE-EDU
15.10.2014	LOSC	Lošov	49.6218	17.3717	IPE-MONET
24.7.2015	SUPC	Skalka u Prostějova	49.3977	17.1720	IPE-MONET
Sep 2015	MAUC	Maruška	49.3655	17.8278	IG-AlpArray
19.11.2015	LUKC	Luká	49.6543	16.9742	IPE-MONET

Fig. 2-4: Map with the seismic stations closest to Zar-3 site.

The CO₂ storage site Zar-3 is located just in the center of seismic stations VRAC, SUPC, KRUC, SEDU and JAVC. The closest station is VRAC in the distance of 39.7 km. At a distance of less than 50 km there are other three stations SUPC, KRUC and SEDU. The detectability of such network is not high in the place of site Zar-3. Location

errors of possible events from the vicinity of site Zar-3 would be large and there is no way to determine reliable event depth without station above event.

In order to assess the seismicity in the vicinity of the CO₂ storage site Zar-3 a local seismic network have to be installed and operated.

The Fig. 2-5 shows locations of 126 tectonic earthquakes together with their depths that have occurred within a distance of 50 km from the CO₂ storage site Zar-3 since 1976. The majority of events are located in the Nysa-Morava Zone —a Late Cenozoic tectonically active region of the NE Bohemian Massif situated at its contact with the Western Carpathians' orogenic front. These events are in the depth range 15 to 30 km. Several shallower events (around 5 km depth) occurred in The White Carpathians region. The five closest events to the storage Žarošice are summarized in Tab. 2-4.

Tab. 2-4: Seismic events in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site

Origin time	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Depth [km]	Mag	Place
1990-05-23 06:47:23	49.1	16.89	--	--	Kobeřice u Brna
1990-10-16 11:12:16	49.07	16.81	--	--	Otnice
1999-10-15 12:10:15	49.02	17.1	--	--	Boršov
2003-09-24 23:58:45	49.06	16.88	16	0.9	Lovčičky
2019-03-19 02:11:19	48.99	16.84	--	--	Šitbořice

To determine reliably depth of event the good station coverage is needed. This is not always satisfied for weaker events and then a false depth of 0 km is issued. In the case that an event is located near a station, the chance of determining the depth is significantly higher.

Fig. 2-5: Map with seismic events since 1976 in the vicinity of Zar-3 storage site. Color of dot corresponds to event depth.

The map with the locations of 126 seismic events from the vicinity of our area of interest displaying the local magnitude is on the Fig. 2-6. The magnitude range of these events is 0.1 to 1.8.

Fig. 2-6: Map with seismic events since 1976 in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site. Color of dot corresponds to event magnitude.

2.3 Summation of historical seismicity

The analysis of earthquakes with macroseismic effect in Zar-3 area is based on the two catalogues. The first one is catalogues of historical earthquakes, it is dated back to 998 year, and obviously this catalogue may not be completed.

The second source of data are seismic bulletins in their digital form (since 1976). Also this data sets are not fully homogeneous, namely due to development of the Network configuration.

For Zar-3 area and its near vicinity (distance < 30 km), there are reported 263 macroseismic observations from 26 strong earthquakes (the more distance ones are from Montenegro and Romany, both of them with epicentral distances greater than 750 km). In addition, there was found 126 relatively weak events in the vicinity of 50 km from Zar-3 site since 1976. Rather high ambiguity in the depth determination of these events is consequence of lack of closest station(s).

Estimated value of maximal acceleration in the area did not exceed 0.1 g in any case.

3 SEISMIC MONITORING ARRAY

The seismic monitoring array was deployed near CO₂ storage site Zar-3 from August 30th, 2021 to August 31st, 2023. Its purpose was to record natural seismicity before the CO₂ storage will start operations. The array consists from five permanent stations. Twice, additional six stations were temporarily deployed for a period of one month, always during the period when the step rate test was supposed to take place. The report describes earthquakes recorded by this monitoring array.

The permanent stations were equipped with sensors Lennartz LE-3D and recorders Vistec Gaia 2T. Sensors LE-3D have own frequency / period 1 s / 1 Hz and sensitivity (gain) 400 V/m/s. The sampling 250 Hz was used. Gaia 2T is a recorder with a dynamic range of 138 dBp-p, synchronization using of the GPS system, by recording data on SD cards, enabling the sending of SMS messages, the sampling frequency was 250 Hz. This equipment is intended for field measurements during both short-term and long-term seismic experiments. The five permanent stations were installed around CO₂ storage site Zar-3 (Fig. 3-1, Tab. 3-1). Their positions were selected to optimize detection and location of seismic events from the (expected) depth around 2-3 km. The permanent stations were operating near Zar-3 storage site whole period of seismic monitoring, i.e. from August 30th, 2021 to August 31st, 2023.

The stations operated in autonomous mode, in triggering regime, with daily status report; the data were stored on SD-card and periodically collected. The internal time was synchronized by GPS. All the system was powered from a battery charged from a solar panel. All the devices (but the antennas and solar panel) were closed in a protecting box (Fig. 3-2). To ensure good coupling condition, these boxes were screwed to the concrete desk, which were deployed round the (non-operated) wells. One station was situated close to a waterworks in an under-surface shelter.

Fig. 3-1: Map with local seismic array near Zar-3 storage site. Rectangles represent our areas of interest and triangles deployed seismic stations.

Tab. 3-1: List of permanent seismic stations

Station	Place	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]
MND01	Násedlovice	49.0052669	16.9540192
MND02	Písečná	49.0640153	16.9034850
MND03	Vrčava	49.0950069	16.9614731
MND04	Žarošice	49.0559761	16.9694406
MND05	Archlebov	49.0474542	17.0046714

The temporary stations were equipped with nodes Magseis Fairfield ZLAND 3C. It contains three internal geophones orthogonal system with frequency 10 Hz, sensitivity (gain) 78.7 V/m/s and with a dynamic range of 127 dB. The node has an operating life 35 days (840 hours). The sampling frequency was 250 Hz; the time base was provided by internal clock (previously synchronized with GPS) and optionally also by GPS. The sensors were shallow buried (few centimetres) under the surface and operated in completely autonomous mode.

The temporary stations were operating in two periods, the first one from November 2nd, 2021 to December 7th, 2021 and the second one from May 16th, 2022 to June 15th, 2022. During these periods the step-rate-test was to be held on CO₂ storage

site Zar-3. The six temporary stations were installed around CO₂ storage site Zar-3 (Fig. 3-2, Tab. 3-2).

Tab. 3-2: List of temporal seismic stations

Station	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Altitude [m]
100	49.04142	16.95200	217.9
101	49.03706	16.97894	226.0
102	49.04861	16.97801	274.7
103	49.05936	16.98889	297.9
104	49.05908	16.96785	233.9
105	49.07165	16.94785	284.7

Fig. 3-2: Seismological monitoring at the Zar-3 site. Seismic monitoring station (left) powered by the solar panel (middle). Deployment of the temporal seismic network on the right.

During a Step-Rate-Test (SRT) in December 2023, the installed seismic network had not been operated any more, therefore a temporal denser network was installed. It consisted of 11 stations equipped by ZATLAND 3C (Magseis Fairfield) independent instruments – the same as for the previously operated temporal stations. This denser network was designed and installed with the intention to study in dine details any activity possibly induced by the test. The points of observation were also the same as for the previous networks.

4 SEISMIC MONITORING DATA PROCESSING

4.1 Data processing

Our local seismic monitoring array of permanent (and occasionally temporal) stations was used for detection and location of seismic events. To improve our results this array was completed by the closest stations of Czech Regional Seismic Network (Fig. 4-1, Tab. 4-1). In order to better detect and locate the events, we used the data measured at the three stations of Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno Vranov (VRAC), Moravský Krumlov (KRUC) and Skalka u Prostějova (SUPC).

Fig. 4-1: Map with seismic stations used for processing of data.

Tab. 4-1: List of seismic stations in the surroundings of CO₂ storage site

Station	Operated since	Place	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Operated by
KRUC	27.9.1993	Moravský Krumlov	49.0619	16.3952	IPE
VRAC	4.11.1993	Vranov	49.3084	16.5933	IPE
SEDU	9.9.2014	Štěpánovský lom	48.9570	16.3306	IPE-EDU
SUPC	24.7.2015	Skalka u Prostějova	49.3977	17.1720	IPE-MONET

As the deployed stations recorded data in off-line mode, the measured data were processed in consecutive months. After the pre-processing (data downloading and reformatting) the same two step procedure as previously was applied: (1) by preliminary automatic picking and (2) by manual detailed interpretation of relevant seismograms – an example see in Fig. 4-7.

During the data processing, the periodically repeated event occurred at 01:59 UTC were identified as an artefact caused by accidental coincidence of GMS status messages sent automatically (with small time drift) by autonomous network stations.

4.2 Observed seismic events in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site

During our monitoring more than 800 seismic events were detected and located. However, majority of these are recorded blasts from nearby quarries (Lom Tasovice, Kamenolom Olbramovice, Lom Dolní Kounice, Lom Želešice, Kamenolom Vícenice, Lomy cementárny Mokrý, Kamenolom Luleč, Kamenolom Lhota Rapotina, Lom Předklášteří, Lom Mirošov, Lom Ořechov, Starý kamenolom Rohožník na Záhorí, Kamenolom Trstín, Kamenolom Čachtice). We have also registered more than 150 detections of some signal of non-tectonic origin connected with operations near Zar-3 storage site (Fig.4-2).

Fig. 4-2: Map with the seismic events from the period of monitoring. Orange dots – anthropogenic events, blue dots – tectonic events.

Except the anthropogenic events mentioned above our local seismic array recorded 103 seismic events probably of tectonic origin (Fig. 4-2). Location of ten events that are in the distance less than 50 km from Zar-3 CO₂ storage site are listed in the Tab. 2-4. These events were located at Hornomoravský úval (Tovačov, Troubky, Přerov etc.). Some events occurred at Oderské vrchy (Šternberk). These strongest events are mainly located in seismically active The White Carpathians region (Fig.4-3). These events are listed in Appendix 2.

Fig. 4-3: Map with the tectonic seismic events from the period of monitoring with marked magnitudes.

The majority of events are located in the Nysa-Morava Zone, Late Cenozoic tectonically active region of the NE Bohemian Massif situated at its contact with the Western Carpathians' orogenic front. These events are in the depth range 15 to 25 km. Several shallower events (around 5 km depth) occurred in The White Carpathians mountains.

No event was detected in the vicinity of Zar-3 storage site during our monitoring period. The potentially local events were identified with quarry blasts, from quarries which are located in the area (Fig.4-4). Regularly there were recorded also events from partly distant areas as Ostrava/Paskov or Lubin (Poland). The pronounced earthquake from Turkey (6 Feb 2023, M=7.8) was detected, too.

Fig. 4-4: Position of local quarries in the region with the located events.

Only one event was located closer than 10 km, between Lovčičky and Žarošice in September 24th, 2003 (i.e. about 10 years before our monitoring started). Its depth was around 16 km (error is about 5 km) and local magnitude 0.9.

4.3 Step-Rate-Test monitoring

The Step-Rate-Test (SRT) on the ZA7 well was carried out on 19 December 2023. The test itself was preceded by necessary repairs of the underground equipment of the well - replacement of the tubing column and installation of a depth gauge with recording.

The SRT was designed to verify the reservoir absorption capacity for 3 different modes (170, 240, 310 l/min), each for 3 hours. A cementing unit MPU - 400 with pressure and flow recording capability was used for the test. A total of 135 m³ of working fluid (reservoir and aquifer water) was collected in the buffer tanks at the center.

The SRT began with an effort to refill the probe with fluid to minimum flow pressure of 0.1 MPa, but this was not achieved. After approximately one hour, the test itself was started with the first mode 170 l/min. Instead of the expected pressure increase, the pressure stabilized of -0,07 MPa, even after approximately 2 hours it was not possible to the given mode achieved an increase in the flow pressure and it was therefore decided to change the test procedure - to try to achieve a pressure increase by maximum liters of pushing. Gradually, the pressing mode was increased from 390 l/min. up to approx. 650 l/min., but even after pressing the entire volume of the prepared working fluid (135 m³) the pressure increase was not achieved. The SRT was therefore terminated after only about 5 hours without achieving the planned (expected) results. The recording from

the downhole manometer shows only a minimal increase in bearing pressure (approx. 0.15 MPa) even at the maximum liter of thrust.

As neither permanent nor temporal stations were operated at the time of SRT, we have deployed a local seismic monitoring array of temporal stations to detect and locate possible induced seismic events (Tab. 4-2, Figs. 4-5 and 4-6). The array was operating from December 5th, 2023 to January 10th, 2024, again instruments ZLAND 3C were used and the points of observation were the same or very similar as for permanent or temporal network respectively. Also the data was processed with the same methodology.

Tab. 4-2: List of station to monitor SR test

Station	Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Altitude [m]
100	49.04831	16.97836	278.2
101	49.04736	16.94598	245.2
102	49.05906	16.96785	234.2
103	49.05289	16.99200	293.3
104	49.03708	16.97892	226.6
105	49.07164	16.94785	286.2
106	49.05536	16.96997	253.2
107	49.06395	16.90358	340.7
108	49.09496	16.96172	353.4
109	49.04762	17.00494	254.3
110	49.00506	16.95391	256.3

Fig. 4-5: Map with seismic stations used for monitoring SRT.

Fig. 4-6: Deploying of SRT stations.

During the SRT we observed increasing noise on the closest station 108. On the 2-3 closest station (100, 103 a 106) some signals were observed (Fig. 4-7). These signals may be very weak events, however their signal-to-noise ratios are very low and they are recorded only on few close stations that this hypothesis could not be verified.

Therefore, on the bases of seismic monitoring of the SRT we conclude that no significant induced seismic activity was observed. However, we recommended seismic observation during any future storage activity at the site (as the performed SRT was relatively short, achieved pressure was low and the injected volume was limited).

Fig. 4-7: Example of waveforms on station 106 during SRT.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

On the bases of our investigation mentioned above, we summarize: neither historical or bulletin data nor our monitoring confirm any significant seismic activity at the Zar-3 site. This conclusion is based on: (i) Macroseismic Report and (ii) Report of site monitoring. Macroseismic report is based on (a) historical events with known macroseismic effect and (b) recorded tectonic events which were recorded in the vicinity of the area. This data was obtained from seismic bulletins and from macroseismic archive of Geophysical Inst. It follows from the Macroseismic report **that estimated value of maximal acceleration in the area did not exceed 0.1 g in any case.**

During direct seismic observation there was observed any seismic activity neither at the site nor in its vicinity. On the other hand, there are commonly recorded events from Lubin (Poland) or Ostrava (both mining areas with induced seismicity) or from close Carpathian system unit, e.g. from Austrian/Hungarian border or for Slovakia – Dobra Voda site; the strong teleseismic events were recorded also.

All the observed local events were identified with query blasts in the nearby queries ((Lom Tasovice, Kamenolom Olbramovice, Lom Dolní Kounice, Lom Želešice, Kamenolom Vícenice, Lomy cementárny Mokrá, Kamenolom Luleč, Kamenolom Lhota Rapotina, Lom Předklášteří, Lom Mirošov, Lom Ořechov, Starý kameňolom Rohožník na Záhorí, Kameňolom Trstín, Kameňolom Čachtice).

As it has been already concluded, **no event was detected in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Žarošice during our monitoring period.** Only one event was located in about 10 km distance, between Lovčičky and Žarošice in September 24th, 2003. Its depth was around 16 km (error is about 5 km) and local magnitude 0.9.¹ – Fig.5-1. The details are given in Seismic Monitoring Report.

¹ Due to low number of that time operated stations, their distances from the event and weakness of the event, the location as well as the magnitude poses relatively high error.

5.2 Possible configurations of seismic network

The configuration and extension of (future) seismic monitoring network will be derived of detailed specification of required outputs. In general, there are two possibilities: (i) only monitoring of (possible) seismic activity at the site and its vicinity is required or (ii) also in addition some information about sources of activity is desirable. It means e.g. information about source orientation (expressed e.g. as source moment tensor) or cracks opening and their spreading, etc. In the former case a network of about 5 stations² is sufficient; in the latter, the network of 10 or more stations³ is needed.

Fig. 5-1: Position of close tectonic event.

² A seismic event location is 4 parameters problem (3 spatial and 1 time coordinates have to be determined). Five station offers (in an ideal case) five data items for P wave onsets and five data items for S wave onsets; however, the ideal amount of data could not be guaranteed for every event, therefore we consider 5 stations network as a reasonable minimum for location task.

³ The source Moment Tensor (MT), which describe seismic source orientation, has 6 parameters. As usage of S waves for MT determination is problematic, the reasonable minimum observations is 10 or more in this case.

6 TECHNICAL NOTES

6.1 Seismic station deployment

It follows from the latest analysis (e.g. Eisner et al., 2010), that deploying of the stations into a borehole with depth of first tens of meters does not improve signal to noise ratio significantly taking into account increased costs of station deployment due to the borehole drilling. Therefore, we recommend surface installation of the stations.

On the other hand, there is no doubt, that shallow digging of stations (first decimeters or meters) can significantly eliminate some types of noise (e.g. noise caused by wind). The other types of artificial noise can be often eliminated by careful selection of a station site. We therefore recommend short testing measurement (e.g. one or several days) on the proposed site before final station deploying.

6.2 Possibly expected scientific results

As mentioned above, we consider at least 5 stations network sufficient for basic monitoring of the repository site and its vicinity. But any new and original seismic scientific results probably may not be obtained from these data. The wider network composed of more than 10 seismic stations has a potential for gain of some scientific results, however the installation of such network will not guarantee such results.

REFERENCES

85/2012 Sb. Zákon o ukládání oxidu uhličitého do přírodních horninových struktur a o změně některých zákonů [WWW Document], n.d. URL

<https://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/2012-85#cast4> (accessed 5.23.23).

Eisner, L., Hulsey, B.J., Duncan, P., Jurick, D., Werner, H., Keller, W., 2010. Comparison of surface and borehole locations of induced seismicity. *Geophys. Prospect.* 58, 809–820. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2478.2010.00867.x>

Směrnice Evropského parlamentu a Rady 2009/31/ES : mojeEnergie [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://www.mojeenergie.cz/cz/smernice-evropskeho-parlamentu-a-rady-2009-31-es> (accessed 5.23.23).

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Catalogue tectonic events

abraviations:

GFU - Institute of Geophysics

ISC - International Seismic Centre

IPE - Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno

MONET - Moravian network, Institute of Physics of the Earth, Masaryk University, Brno

Datetime [UTC]	Lat	Lon	Depth [km]	ML	Agency	Comment
1980-04-12 10:52:12,0	48,90	17,10	0		GFU	
1980-05-08 11:06:08,0	49,46	16,77	0		GFU	
1980-10-03 16:03:03,0	49,20	16,70	0		GFU	
1981-01-17 09:58:17,0	48,76	17,21	0		GFU	
1981-10-21 20:01:21,0	49,25	17,29	0		GFU	
1982-07-12 05:51:12,0	48,90	17,50	0		GFU	
1982-09-14 13:34:14,0	49,30	16,89	0		GFU	
1985-08-02 16:00:02,0	49,41	17,39	0		GFU	
1987-02-13 12:35:13,0	49,30	17,40	0		GFU	
1987-08-21 12:16:21,0	49,00	17,40	0		GFU	
1987-12-18 13:30:18,0	49,37	16,87	0		GFU	
1988-02-11 10:50:11,0	49,36	16,51	0		GFU	
1988-03-22 11:35:22,0	49,33	16,85	10		ISC	
1989-02-24 15:04:24,0	48,80	16,60	0		GFU	
1990-05-23 06:47:23,0	49,10	16,89	0		GFU	
1990-10-16 11:12:16,0	49,07	16,81	0		GFU	
1992-02-28 10:49:28,0	49,30	16,80	0		GFU	
1992-09-24 13:50:24,0	49,20	17,40	0		GFU	
1993-08-12 17:37:12,0	49,23	16,66	0		GFU	
1994-10-12 14:25:12,0	49,21	16,91	0		GFU	
1994-12-21 13:11:21,0	49,10	17,60	0		GFU	explosion ?
1995-10-31 00:24:31,0	49,30	16,50	0		GFU	
1995-12-01 01:19:01,0	49,30	17,20	0		GFU	
1996-07-02 16:37:02,0	48,70	17,30	0		GFU	
1996-12-09 11:01:09,0	48,94	17,34	0		GFU	
1997-03-14 13:01:14,0	49,38	17,08	0		GFU	
1997-04-21 04:32:21,0	48,68	17,29	0		GFU	
1997-05-15 16:50:15,0	49,05	16,57	0		GFU	
1997-05-22 00:31:22,0	49,05	17,44	0		GFU	
1997-08-26 14:01:26,0	48,80	17,36	0		GFU	
1997-10-06 15:18:06,0	49,13	16,65	0		GFU	
1997-10-29 13:48:29,0	49,22	17,30	0		GFU	

1998-02-05 15:07:05,0	49,10	17,40	0		GFU	
1998-09-30 13:18:30,0	48,90	16,41	0		GFU	
1998-11-27 14:47:27,0	49,19	16,34	0		GFU	
1999-03-11 16:23:11,0	48,70	16,98	0		GFU	
1999-05-12 06:54:12,0	49,38	17,01	0		GFU	
1999-06-18 08:38:18,0	49,20	16,59	0		GFU	
1999-10-15 12:10:15,0	49,02	17,10	0		GFU	
2000-06-02 11:31:02,0	49,12	16,61	0		GFU	
2000-08-17 11:37:17,0	49,02	16,30	0		GFU	
2000-09-04 18:23:04,0	48,78	17,02	0		GFU	
2000-09-29 11:04:29,0	48,99	16,45	0		GFU	
2000-10-16 12:00:16,0	49,26	16,99	0	1,8	GFU	
2001-01-28 16:50:28,0	49,44	17,19	19		IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2002-05-11 19:33:11,0	49,32	17,43	16		IPE	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2003-09-24 23:58:24,0	49,06	16,94	3	0,7	IPE	tectonic event, Uhřice
2004-03-24 17:20:24,0	48,75	17,14	0		GFU	
2004-03-26 11:08:26,0	49,29	17,29	15	1,1	IPE	tectonic event, Vsetín
2004-06-01 03:48:01,0	48,83	16,98	0		GFU	
2004-12-18 21:21:18,0	48,62	17,06	0		GFU	
2004-12-28 23:18:28,0	48,86	17,15	10		GFU	
2005-03-09 10:41:09,0	48,89	17,12	0		GFU	
2005-03-21 16:57:21,0	49,43	17,14	0		GFU	tectonic event; IPE
2005-07-22 20:45:22,0	49,33	17,30	0		GFU	tectonic event; IPE
2006-02-20 19:35:20,0	49,12	17,34	0	1	GFU	
2006-04-16 00:20:16,0	49,20	16,87	0		GFU	
2006-10-14 19:53:14,0	49,44	17,21	20	1,6	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2006-10-28 21:26:28,0	49,45	17,10	0		GFU	tectonic event, SSE of Svitavy
2006-11-07 14:03:07,0	49,17	16,41	0		GFU	
2006-11-19 08:09:19,0	49,35	17,30	0		GFU	tectonic event, Tovačov
2006-12-17 23:52:17,0	49,34	17,27	0		GFU	
2007-02-16 16:46:16,0	49,38	17,36	0		GFU	tectonic event
2007-06-25 20:26:25,0	49,46	17,25	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2008-04-30 22:26:30,0	49,46	17,04	14	0,8	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2008-08-05 20:27:05,0	48,63	17,15	0		GFU	Slovakia
2008-10-18 15:50:18,0	49,34	17,38	13	1,1	IPE	tectonic event, Chropyně
2008-11-18 05:19:18,0	49,39	17,29	0		GFU	tectonic event, N Moravia
2009-05-15 11:28:15,0	49,10	17,58	7	1,4	IPE	tectonic event, Uherské Hradiště
2009-07-11 20:36:11,0	49,29	17,53	9	0,6	IPE	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2009-07-12 01:55:12,0	49,27	17,55	9	0	IPE	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2009-07-28 04:59:28,0	49,45	17,26	18	1,1	IPE	tectonic event, Tovačov
2010-07-05 15:17:05,0	49,38	17,08	0		GFU	tectonic event, Moravia
2010-12-26 01:06:26,0	49,41	17,25	0		GFU	tectonic event, N Moravia
2011-04-10 01:24:10,0	49,43	17,33	21	0,2	MONET	tectonic event, Troubky
2011-05-01 23:34:01,0	49,25	17,51	10	0,2	MONET	tectonic event, Tlumačov
2012-03-06 01:20:06,0	48,62	17,15	9		GFU	Studienka

2012-03-06 13:32:06,0	48,62	17,11	4	1	GFU	Studienka
2012-06-01 19:56:01,0	49,42	17,35	20	0,1	IPE	tectonic event, Troubky
2012-07-09 22:21:09,0	49,42	17,34	0		GFU	tectonic event, Central Moravia
2013-07-22 19:55:22,0	49,39	17,28	20		MONET	tectonic event, Lobodice
2013-08-02 21:07:02,0	49,41	17,21	22		MONET	tectonic event, Prostějov
2013-09-08 01:39:08,0	49,32	17,06	23		MONET	tectonic event, Drysice
2013-09-15 03:48:15,0	49,44	17,24	22	0,1	MONET	tectonic event, Tovačov
2013-10-19 10:09:19,0	49,41	17,18	22	0,2	MONET	tectonic event, Prostějov, Skalka
2013-11-11 09:51:11,0	49,37	17,27	22	1,4	MONET	tectonic event, Kojetín
2014-01-07 03:19:07,0	49,22	17,48	17	1,8	IPE	tectonic event, Otrokovice
2014-03-30 06:42:30,0	49,29	17,44	16	0,5	IPE	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2014-04-27 08:27:27,0	49,34	17,32	0		GFU	tectonic event, Central Moravia
2014-05-11 15:34:11,0	49,29	17,17	0		GFU	tectonic event, Nezamyslice
2014-07-03 00:48:03,0	49,40	17,33	2	0,7	GFU	tectonic event
2015-02-13 16:25:13,0	49,38	17,38	0		GFU	tectonic event, Troubky
2015-02-13 16:26:13,0	49,36	17,38	0		GFU	tectonic event, Troubky
2015-02-13 16:27:13,0	49,37	17,37	0		GFU	tectonic event, Troubky
2015-02-14 04:04:14,0	49,36	17,39	0		GFU	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2015-08-27 09:11:27,0	49,39	17,39	0		GFU	tectonic event, Troubky
2015-08-29 09:46:29,0	49,44	17,09	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2015-08-29 09:47:29,0	49,43	17,10	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2015-09-10 02:28:10,0	49,43	17,10	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2015-09-10 02:29:10,0	49,43	17,10	0	0,5	GFU	
2015-10-19 03:29:19,0	48,70	17,32	0	0,7	GFU	
2015-12-25 03:37:25,0	49,49	17,03	1	0,8	GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2016-04-27 16:17:27,0	49,41	17,30	0		GFU	tectonic event, Troubky
2016-06-07 14:57:07,0	49,47	17,09	23	0,3	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2016-07-25 17:23:25,0	49,48	17,05	13	0,5	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2016-07-25 20:07:25,0	49,48	17,05	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2016-08-02 20:57:02,0	49,43	17,34	23		IPE	tectonic event, Troubky
2016-08-14 12:00:14,0	49,35	17,24	33	0,5	IPE	tectonic event, Kojetín
2016-08-24 21:47:24,0	49,04	16,51	13		IPE	tectonic event, Némčičky
2016-10-09 00:08:09,0	48,75	16,78	26	0,6	IPE	tectonic event, Valtice
2017-04-04 22:49:04,0	49,47	17,05	14	0,1	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2017-07-30 08:48:30,0	49,28	17,33	19		IPE	tectonic event, Kroměříž
2017-09-15 01:16:15,0	49,45	17,12	23	0,4	IPE	tectonic event, Prostějov
2017-10-24 18:05:24,0	49,41	17,25	20		IPE	tectonic event, Tovačov
2018-10-28 04:15:28,0	49,21	17,20	0		GFU	tectonic event, Morkovice
2019-01-07 04:14:07,0	48,70	17,23	1		GFU	tectonic event, Šternberk
2019-01-17 02:11:17,0	49,38	17,30	0		GFU	tectonic event, Tovačov
2019-03-19 02:11:19,0	48,99	16,84	0		GFU	tectonic event, Šitbořice
2019-04-03 04:49:03,0	49,38	17,26	0		GFU	tectonic event, Prostějov
2019-08-15 05:30:15,0	49,15	16,66	0		GFU	
2019-08-23 10:17:23,0	49,37	17,28	0		GFU	tectonic event, Tovačov
2019-11-06 08:29:06,0	49,39	17,40	0		GFU	tectonic event, Přerov

2019-12-14 21:17:14,0	49,33	17,32	0		GF	tectonic event, Kojetín
2019-12-27 19:44:27,0	49,38	17,34	0		GFU	tectonic event, Tovačov
2020-03-23 03:19:23,0	49,26	17,10	17	0,6	IPE	tectonic event, Moravské Málkovice
2020-03-26 01:20:26,0	49,47	17,05	0		GFU	tectonic event, Konice

Appendix 2: Recorded seismic events

Date Time	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	Mag type	Mag	
2021-08-30 08:36:56,5	49,2973	16,3748	0	ML	1,8	A
2021-08-30 12:10:01,8	48,5817	17,6082	0	ML	0,8	A
2021-08-31 06:02:59,8	48,4440	17,3320	0	ML	0,6	A
2021-08-31 08:23:06,7	48,4757	17,5178	0	ML	1,5	A
2021-08-31 08:49:16,4	49,2305	16,9400	0	ML	1,9	A
2021-09-01 11:10:45,9	49,2195	16,1058	0	ML	1,8	A Vícenice
2021-09-01 12:30:15,5	48,6162	15,8508	0	ML	1,4	A
2021-09-02 07:40:07,5	49,3036	16,3888	0	ML	2,1	A
2021-09-03 07:59:24,8	48,8170	16,1650	0	ML	1,6	A Hodonice
2021-09-03 11:20:23,0	49,2911	16,5870	0	ML	1,9	A
2021-09-04 11:58:45,0	49,4619	17,3086	20	ML	0	T Tovačov
2021-09-06 03:12:35,4	49,6636	17,2928	15	ML	0,1	T J od Šternberka, Bohuňovice
2021-09-06 13:04:11,7	48,8535	15,5915	0	ML	1,2	A
2021-09-07 01:49:40,3	48,5920	17,7210	2	ML	0,9	T Vrbové
2021-09-07 07:42:55,7	49,0045	16,3164	0	ML	1,7	A Olbramovice
2021-09-07 07:47:39,2	49,3637	16,3987	0	ML	1,7	A
2021-09-07 08:27:38,6	48,4810	17,5093	0	ML	1,5	A
2021-09-07 08:52:07,1	49,3449	17,0770	0	ML	1,6	A
2021-09-07 09:35:53,6	48,5364	17,4443	0	ML	1,2	A
2021-09-07 21:48:40,5	48,9500	18,3880	11	ML	0,9	T Košecké Rovné
2021-09-08 09:59:31,4	48,4161	17,2818	0	ML	1,6	A
2021-09-08 10:03:41,8	49,3349	16,4675	0	ML	2,1	A
2021-09-09 08:00:02,4	49,3242	17,6650	0	ML	1,9	A
2021-09-09 20:52:58,5	49,6180	17,7920	21	ML	0,1	T Odry
2021-09-10 07:53:38,7	48,4005	17,2265	0	ML	1,2	A
2021-09-11 05:20:35,3	48,4124	17,1336	3	ML	1,0	T Kuchyňa
2021-09-14 07:06:58,1	49,2163	16,7107	0	ML	1,8	A
2021-09-14 09:45:20,2	49,6721	16,9769	0	ML	1,8	A
2021-09-14 09:47:31,4	49,6706	16,9745	0	ML	1,7	A
2021-09-15 07:46:31,5	48,9915	16,3261	0	ML	1,6	A Olbramovice
2021-09-15 07:54:19,7	49,6669	17,2927	14	ML	0,6	T J od Šternberka, Bohuňovice
2021-09-15 13:52:17,2	49,4300	17,3600	23	ML	0,0	T Troubky
2021-09-15 14:10:03,8	49,4310	17,3640	22	ML	0,0	T Troubky
2021-09-15 14:18:05,5	49,4280	17,3640	23	ML	0,0	T Troubky
2021-09-17 07:17:18,0	49,2321	16,7146	0	ML	1,8	A
2021-09-17 07:50:28,1	49,4248	16,6033	0	ML	2	A
2021-09-17 09:55:30,1	48,7550	17,7710	0	ML	1,4	A
2021-09-17 10:49:55,3	48,5561	17,3836	0	ML	1,8	A
2021-09-20 09:59:38,9	48,4349	17,2976	0	ML	2	A
2021-09-21 08:21:23,2	49,4193	16,0526	0	ML	1,7	A
2021-09-22 12:31:42,2	48,6191	15,9106	0	ML	1,8	A

2021-09-24 07:54:33,0	49,2042	16,6844	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-09-24 08:06:55,7	49,4674	16,1376	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-09-27 08:27:50,1	49,2350	16,9259	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-09-29 07:35:22,0	49,0899	16,4201	0	ML	1,8	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-09-29 16:35:35,4	49,6300	17,7720	23	ML	0,0	T	JZ od Oder, Jindřichov
2021-09-30 00:44:43,2	49,7420	17,3710	18	ML	0,0	T	SV od Šternberka, Těšíkov
2021-09-30 10:06:03,2	49,6594	16,3537	0	ML	2	A	
2021-09-30 12:55:56,6	49,6092	17,4205	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-09-30 14:28:01,7	49,0121	16,3154	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2021-10-01 11:36:03,4	49,2086	16,1217	0	ML	1,5	A	Vícenice
2021-10-04 07:24:57,3	49,3382	16,0488	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-10-04 07:38:04,5	49,4445	16,6233	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-10-04 07:47:32,5	49,2102	16,6929	0	ML	1,4	A	
2021-10-04 09:10:27,6	48,5309	17,4330	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-10-05 07:22:59,9	49,1743	16,9045	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-10-05 09:08:18,8	48,9650	18,2570	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-10-05 09:13:36,7	49,4355	16,0400	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-10-05 11:22:05,7	48,8543	15,5779	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-10-06 04:06:29,6	48,4163	17,1314	5	ML	1,7	T	Kuchyňa
2021-10-06 10:41:37,3	49,1226	16,5397	0	ML	1,8	A	Želešice
2021-10-06 12:17:46,9	48,6202	15,8797	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-10-07 08:27:31,7	49,4306	16,1619	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-10-08 07:20:37,4	48,4173	17,3028	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-10-08 07:59:22,5	49,4548	16,6221	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-10-11 00:12:28,0	48,6401	17,4033	4	ML	0,6	T	Senica
2021-10-11 07:33:06,0	49,0710	16,4508	0	ML	1,4	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-10-11 07:54:08,3	49,6679	16,3768	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-10-12 07:51:07,9	49,2115	16,7484	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-10-12 07:56:58,5	48,5103	17,5023	0	ML	1,3	A	
2021-10-12 08:12:47,7	48,7772	16,2384	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-12 08:59:29,7	48,3954	17,3017	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-10-12 10:00:24,1	48,1451	16,9928	0	ML	1,3	A	
2021-10-12 11:47:06,8	48,9501	15,6511	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-10-12 13:00:24,6	48,5928	17,6299	0	ML	0,7	A	
2021-10-13 07:46:47,2	49,0926	16,4026	0	ML	1,4	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-10-13 09:35:10,8	48,5090	17,4690	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-13 11:14:13,9	48,6134	15,8466	0	ML	1,2	A	
2021-10-15 08:00:36,4	48,5310	16,3100	0	ML	0,9	A	
2021-10-15 08:33:46,5	48,8526	15,5888	0	ML	1	A	
2021-10-15 08:33:52,0	48,8532	15,6051	0	ML	1,2	A	
2021-10-15 09:00:04,9	48,3936	17,2994	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-10-15 11:20:25,9	49,1213	16,5349	0	ML	1,5	A	Želešice
2021-10-18 10:30:54,5	48,4135	17,2745	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-19 07:37:24,7	48,8054	16,1534	0	ML	1,4	A	Hodonice
2021-10-19 07:49:18,4	49,4453	16,6316	0	ML	1,9	A	

2021-10-20 07:44:12,7	49,2101	16,7465	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-20 09:13:11,1	48,9330	16,4077	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-20 09:48:22,4	48,4844	17,5305	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-10-21 09:50:57,4	49,1157	16,5004	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-10-22 07:58:06,8	49,2532	16,7103	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-25 08:50:34,2	49,2451	16,9448	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-10-25 09:18:33,2	49,3711	16,3933	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-10-26 09:53:37,0	49,2907	16,2333	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-10-27 08:22:51,9	49,5392	16,0519	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-10-27 09:01:36,8	49,2425	16,8810	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-10-28 11:20:43,2	48,6150	15,8736	0	ML	1	A	
2021-10-31 22:23:48,3	48,2500	16,0240	9	ML	0,5	T	Ried am Riederberg
2021-11-01 09:45:42,6	49,2372	16,9067	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-11-01 10:39:05,7	49,1236	16,5394	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2021-11-02 12:16:27,8	48,9689	15,8757	0	ML	1	A	
2021-11-02 13:07:57,4	48,5964	15,8640	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-03 08:55:49,9	49,3432	16,3537	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-03 12:23:21,9	48,8570	15,5764	0	ML	1,2	A	
2021-11-04 09:29:29,4	49,2025	16,9459	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-04 09:41:24,9	48,8064	16,1652	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2021-11-04 11:00:27,9	48,1145	16,9604	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-05 09:18:03,5	49,4178	16,5669	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-11-05 09:33:59,4	49,2160	16,8362	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-06 23:00:06,1	49,6144	17,7586	21	ML	0,6	T	Střítež nad Ludinou
2021-11-08 08:58:11,5	48,5901	17,4885	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-08 09:56:24,4	48,5887	17,4403	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-08 10:01:00,1	49,6552	16,3264	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-08 13:08:37,5	49,1931	16,1345	0	ML	1,4	A	Vícenice
2021-11-09 08:30:18,4	49,0929	16,4356	0	ML	1,8	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-11-10 08:18:12,3	49,1891	16,8442	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-11-10 14:06:19,9	49,1785	16,4261	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-11-10 14:27:42,3	48,5333	15,9828	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-11-12 08:36:15,4	48,8272	16,1521	0	ML	1,8	A	Hodonice
2021-11-12 09:30:00,0	48,5149	17,5075	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-11-12 09:34:22,8	48,9755	16,4873	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-16 08:38:18,4	49,1953	16,3375	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-16 09:31:11,7	49,4400	16,1376	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-11-16 10:28:25,4	49,3497	16,3545	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-11-19 03:10:34,0	48,1816	16,6646	16	ML	0,7	T	Orth an der Donau
2021-11-19 08:58:28,6	48,6110	15,8446	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-11-22 08:51:06,3	48,5490	17,4080	0	ML	1	A	
2021-11-22 09:49:53,2	49,3245	17,1208	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-23 08:41:57,6	49,3470	16,1289	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-23 09:33:42,1	49,3715	16,3820	0	ML	2	A	
2021-11-23 09:58:21,3	48,5458	17,4246	0	ML	1,4	A	

2021-11-24 10:50:14,5	48,6161	15,8336	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-11-24 11:30:00,5	48,4011	17,3008	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-24 13:27:02,0	49,3116	16,5215	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-24 14:40:12,9	48,8579	15,5820	0	ML	1,2	A	
2021-11-25 08:46:50,4	49,2115	16,7204	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-11-25 09:26:59,6	49,4098	16,0392	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-11-29 10:02:22,6	48,4992	17,4382	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-11-29 10:20:14,7	48,6074	15,8481	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-11-29 11:55:30,2	48,9525	15,6538	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-11-30 10:08:13,6	48,6701	17,7405	0	ML	1,4	A	
2021-11-30 10:20:37,5	48,9950	16,3545	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2021-12-01 09:20:15,5	49,4550	16,5827	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-12-01 09:51:29,4	49,5898	15,9026	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-12-03 08:59:42,7	48,3937	17,3927	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-12-06 09:05:30,5	49,0530	16,4608	0	ML	1,5	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-12-06 09:29:57,7	48,8245	16,1467	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2021-12-06 11:52:12,9	49,0696	15,9141	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-12-07 08:51:49,4	49,2032	16,7145	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-12-07 09:07:26,3	49,4434	16,6363	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-12-07 11:44:54,1	49,2041	16,1199	0	ML	1,6	A	Vícenice
2021-12-08 08:02:36,9	48,5085	17,5220	0	ML	2,1	A	
2021-12-08 09:10:11,0	49,0667	16,4631	0	ML	1,6	A	Dolní Kounice
2021-12-10 10:04:27,5	49,2236	16,9339	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-12-10 11:00:33,9	48,1338	17,0237	0	ML	1,8	A	
2021-12-10 14:47:33,7	48,3883	17,2563	0	ML	1,9	A	
2021-12-13 09:51:44,3	48,9990	16,3636	0	ML	1,3	A	Olbramovice
2021-12-14 10:27:36,8	49,1219	16,5384	0	ML	1,7	A	Želešice
2021-12-14 10:28:51,0	49,3138	17,1257	0	ML	1,5	A	
2021-12-14 11:00:21,4	48,1469	17,0028	0	ML	1,7	A	
2021-12-15 03:18:10,9	48,4203	17,0812	0	ML	0,7	T	Malacky
2021-12-15 03:21:03,1	48,3060	17,0340	0	ML	0,3	A	
2021-12-17 12:06:22,5	49,1665	16,4072	0	ML	1,4	A	
2021-12-20 08:53:49,1	49,2092	16,8454	0	ML	1,6	A	
2021-12-21 13:10:59,2	48,8544	15,5760	0	ML	1,3	A	
2021-12-22 11:24:31,4	48,6090	15,8495	0	ML	1,1	A	
2021-12-31 12:40:37,9	48,4250	17,3030	0	ML	0,2	A	
2022-01-01 15:18:49,2	49,9210	17,9040	13	ML	0,5	T	Opava
2022-01-05 17:46:45,4	49,9600	17,8920	14	ML	0,6	T	Opava
2022-01-05 17:46:53,1	49,9510	17,8910	15	ML	0,3	T	Opava
2022-01-05 19:03:48,3	49,9600	17,8920	14	ML	1,4	T	Opava
2022-01-05 19:20:15,2	49,9610	17,8920	14	ML	0,8	T	Opava
2022-01-06 10:42:51,0	49,2981	16,5720	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-01-07 09:37:01,5	49,7310	17,7720	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-01-10 10:44:36,5	49,5950	17,4960	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-01-10 12:20:02,7	48,4160	17,1010	0	ML	1,6	A	

2022-01-11 08:57:24,0	48,8265	16,1243	0	ML	1,2	A	Hodonice
2022-01-11 13:32:38,9	49,2072	16,1203	0	ML	1,7	A	Vícenice
2022-01-13 08:45:55,5	49,2483	16,6904	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-01-13 09:44:07,0	49,2026	16,3383	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-01-15 16:51:42,9	49,7580	17,0580	16	ML	0,1	T	Z od Uničova, Benkov
2022-01-18 10:00:04,7	49,2055	16,7679	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-01-19 09:17:17,5	48,9884	16,3620	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-01-24 08:53:48,5	49,4295	16,0338	0	ML	2	A	
2022-01-24 15:28:41,3	48,8650	15,5919	0	ML	0,8	A	
2022-01-25 09:00:37,9	48,8134	16,1560	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2022-01-25 09:50:55,5	48,5420	17,4090	0	ML	1	A	
2022-01-25 11:00:19,9	48,1321	16,9513	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-01-26 09:07:51,3	49,3393	16,1114	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-01-27 10:06:58,0	49,2783	16,9272	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-01-27 10:59:49,8	48,6112	15,8368	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-01-31 12:23:24,1	48,9498	15,6521	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-02-01 11:00:10,2	48,1808	16,9439	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-02-01 13:51:59,7	48,8447	15,5977	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-02-02 10:37:58,0	49,1116	16,5976	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-02-03 10:24:04,0	48,5944	15,8369	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-02-03 11:00:15,1	48,1307	16,8342	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-02-04 10:00:27,0	48,5920	17,4570	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-02-05 21:10:03,4	48,2050	15,5660	7	ML	0,9	T	St. Pölten
2022-02-10 08:40:51,0	49,1813	16,7401	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-02-11 08:18:48,2	49,3315	16,1347	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-02-11 09:25:16,1	49,2269	16,6934	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-02-11 09:39:06,6	48,9965	16,3604	0	ML	1,8	A	Olbramovice
2022-02-11 09:59:30,4	49,5896	15,9056	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-02-12 15:13:03,2	49,9320	17,9010	12	ML	0,7	T	Opava
2022-02-14 12:37:36,0	49,6210	16,8960	16	ML	0,0	T	S od Konice, Hvozd
2022-02-14 12:41:55,3	48,8562	15,5814	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-02-15 10:50:40,8	48,6200	15,8432	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-02-15 11:01:04,1	48,2075	16,9058	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-02-15 12:23:15,1	49,1534	16,4472	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-02-16 09:26:23,6	49,3658	16,3570	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-02-17 06:48:02,7	49,7370	17,0740	16	ML	0,1	T	S od Litovle, Střelice
2022-02-18 08:36:18,7	49,1858	16,6623	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-02-21 09:17:05,4	49,2264	16,7224	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-02-22 10:27:57,3	49,3779	16,3930	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-02-22 10:30:43,3	49,3625	16,3750	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-02-25 09:36:09,7	48,6007	15,8831	0	ML	0,6	A	
2022-02-26 07:10:36,1	48,5870	17,6600	10	ML	0,9	T	Lančár
2022-02-28 03:23:47,8	48,5274	17,5993	8	ML	0,5	T	Kátlovce
2022-02-28 08:28:40,1	48,9893	16,3509	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2022-02-28 10:41:45,6	48,8599	15,5945	0	ML	1,1	A	

2022-03-01 10:05:14,0	48,8552	15,5830	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-03-02 08:14:45,1	49,2067	16,8307	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-03 07:54:59,1	48,5080	17,3620	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-03-03 08:31:51,8	49,3243	16,3872	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-03-03 09:57:37,6	48,7050	17,7350	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-03-03 10:59:03,5	49,6230	16,9560	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-04 08:15:15,6	49,2265	16,6829	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-03-04 08:58:16,6	49,4623	16,6232	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-07 09:28:00,0	49,4594	16,1293	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-03-08 09:44:03,9	49,2319	16,9216	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-08 09:57:51,2	49,2834	17,1566	0	ML	2	A	
2022-03-08 11:26:37,3	49,0602	15,9079	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-09 09:14:15,2	49,0011	16,3471	0	ML	1,4	A	Olbramovice
2022-03-09 09:32:27,1	49,2184	16,7116	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-10 11:04:57,3	49,2916	16,4827	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-03-10 18:32:12,7	49,2914	16,5345	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-03-11 08:03:17,4	49,0811	16,4635	0	ML	1,4	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-03-11 09:16:11,3	49,3535	16,1287	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-11 10:44:31,0	48,3980	17,0660	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-11 12:25:04,3	48,7176	15,8315	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-03-14 08:14:31,2	49,0609	16,4534	0	ML	1,2	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-03-14 08:19:06,5	49,5505	16,0681	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-14 09:26:46,7	49,4568	16,6047	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-14 10:02:21,7	48,6020	17,4310	0	ML	2	A	
2022-03-15 07:19:45,3	49,2260	16,7181	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-03-15 08:19:06,6	48,9280	18,0890	0	ML	1	A	
2022-03-15 12:42:59,4	48,4210	17,1630	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-16 09:08:38,8	49,4049	16,0324	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-03-16 11:36:10,4	48,8543	15,5777	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-03-17 09:40:20,9	49,2040	16,8793	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-17 16:16:10,9	49,2343	16,6310	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-18 08:15:24,5	48,9992	16,3381	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2022-03-18 10:51:09,6	48,9477	15,6522	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-21 08:54:28,8	49,1918	16,7414	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-21 09:20:41,4	49,2020	16,3333	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-03-21 12:04:33,5	49,6041	15,9158	0	ML	2	A	
2022-03-22 07:09:26,5	48,5130	17,3980	0	ML	0,3	A	
2022-03-22 09:16:21,0	49,3640	15,6158	0	ML	2	A	
2022-03-22 09:31:00,4	48,4130	17,1110	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-03-22 14:11:27,4	48,6330	17,6000	6	ML	1	T	
2022-03-23 03:29:54,9	49,6790	17,5520	17	ML	0,2	T	Město Libavá
2022-03-24 09:09:16,7	49,5050	17,5190	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-24 09:21:26,7	48,5393	17,4902	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-24 10:00:01,5	48,4150	17,0440	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-03-24 11:35:42,6	49,1178	16,5545	0	ML	1,4	A	Želešice

2022-03-25 14:06:53,7	48,9744	15,8880	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-03-28 07:40:37,3	49,4681	16,5948	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-28 09:11:19,0	49,6637	16,3425	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-03-28 10:00:19,4	48,1323	16,9362	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-03-29 08:03:17,3	48,5510	17,4260	0	ML	0,7	A	
2022-03-29 08:09:30,0	49,1222	16,5567	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-03-30 07:24:34,8	49,2207	16,7270	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-03-30 08:59:53,7	48,8144	16,1477	0	ML	1,8	A	Hodonice
2022-03-30 12:59:41,5	49,8500	17,2110	10	ML	0,4	T	Ruda
2022-03-30 20:58:32,2	48,1530	17,0747	6	ML	0,9	T	Bratislava
2022-03-30 20:58:35,2	48,2000	16,9200	6	MV	0,2	T	
2022-03-31 08:48:57,4	49,2155	16,9410	0	ML	2	A	
2022-04-01 07:00:57,3	49,4600	16,5871	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-04-04 07:25:05,8	48,4330	17,1560	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-04-04 10:33:52,1	49,5938	15,9019	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-04-05 07:11:37,9	48,8083	16,1695	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2022-04-05 09:36:48,3	48,6167	15,8494	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-04-05 11:05:43,8	49,2926	16,2523	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-04-06 07:57:36,2	48,9297	16,3992	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-04-06 07:58:39,9	48,5220	17,4620	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-04-07 08:30:36,4	48,8170	16,1660	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2022-04-07 10:51:43,5	49,0795	15,8505	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-04-08 07:46:14,7	49,0159	16,3796	0	ML	1,2	A	Olbramovice
2022-04-08 09:01:07,4	49,6282	16,7914	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-08 11:35:15,3	48,4383	17,1806	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-11 08:16:48,3	48,8185	16,1400	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2022-04-11 14:13:45,8	48,6177	15,8484	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-04-12 07:14:44,3	49,3095	16,8057	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-15 09:00:53,0	48,8455	15,5933	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-04-17 11:43:35,2	48,3214	16,7073	11	ML	0,6	T	Gänserndorf
2022-04-19 08:53:49,2	49,3559	15,6113	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-04-20 07:08:43,1	49,4522	16,6193	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-21 07:18:55,5	49,0897	16,4287	0	ML	1,6	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-04-21 08:32:12,8	49,2623	15,6124	0	ML	2	A	
2022-04-21 11:49:32,9	48,4010	17,1690	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-22 07:39:28,0	49,4213	16,0216	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-04-22 08:37:01,9	49,2148	16,8066	0	ML	2	A	
2022-04-25 07:24:44,0	48,9907	16,3588	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-04-26 06:52:51,0	49,2091	16,6795	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-04-26 08:03:12,9	49,4626	16,1537	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-26 08:51:24,4	48,9800	18,3060	0	ML	0,8	A	
2022-04-26 09:40:03,9	49,2440	16,9430	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-28 07:58:43,1	49,0060	16,3491	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2022-04-28 08:23:53,9	49,2594	16,8941	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-04-28 08:28:22,6	48,5640	17,3750	0	ML	1,8	A	

2022-04-28 08:58:26,0	48,5562	16,3291	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-04-28 09:44:51,3	48,8467	15,6044	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-04-29 07:13:56,9	49,2179	16,7562	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-04-29 08:28:47,0	48,8136	16,1652	0	ML	1,8	A	Hodonice
2022-05-02 08:51:23,3	49,6238	16,3166	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-05-04 07:48:48,1	49,2773	16,9114	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-05-05 08:03:44,2	48,9904	16,3999	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-05-06 07:12:50,3	49,1911	16,7213	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-06 08:24:08,5	49,4393	16,1720	0	ML	2	A	
2022-05-06 08:57:46,6	49,7952	16,1745	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-09 07:13:31,8	49,2290	16,7221	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-09 08:13:14,0	49,4611	16,6226	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-09 09:45:48,1	48,5100	16,5201	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-05-09 10:20:41,6	49,3331	16,4076	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-10 08:50:33,9	49,3589	15,6100	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-05-10 09:51:09,4	49,1265	16,5455	0	ML	1,4	A	Želešice
2022-05-11 19:37:37,0	48,6300	17,4200	3	ML	0,5	T	Osuské
2022-05-12 06:53:24,8	49,2133	16,6834	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-05-13 07:42:30,4	49,2789	16,3698	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-05-14 07:41:22,0	49,6674	17,2925	15	ML	1,5	T	J od Šternberka, Bohuňovice
2022-05-16 07:56:54,7	49,1217	16,5535	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-05-16 09:19:40,3	49,6430	17,1980	0	ML	2	A	
2022-05-17 07:53:14,6	49,3570	17,4620	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-05-17 08:37:17,3	49,1102	16,5649	0	ML	1,7	A	Želešice
2022-05-17 11:12:05,8	49,2103	16,1129	0	ML	1,8	A	Vícenice
2022-05-19 08:27:37,7	49,2108	16,9064	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-05-20 07:15:19,7	49,2275	16,7285	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-20 08:23:31,2	49,4320	16,0351	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-05-20 09:22:33,5	49,5300	17,6250	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-05-23 09:00:50,2	49,3614	15,6216	0	ML	2	A	
2022-05-24 07:51:31,9	49,2192	16,8014	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-05-24 08:27:26,9	48,6330	17,8810	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-24 11:16:23,9	49,2842	16,2445	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-05-25 06:58:44,2	49,2070	16,7770	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-05-25 08:06:08,6	49,4486	16,6188	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-26 07:34:06,6	49,2408	16,7332	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-05-26 09:39:18,6	49,2507	16,9902	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-05-26 10:00:00,6	49,3147	16,4669	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-27 07:31:50,4	49,3452	16,3733	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-05-30 08:20:01,4	49,3707	16,3996	0	ML	2	A	
2022-05-30 08:21:36,2	49,4654	16,1539	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-05-30 10:08:09,3	48,6169	15,8417	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-05-31 08:22:57,0	49,2058	16,7812	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-05-31 08:31:30,5	48,8107	16,1668	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2022-05-31 10:11:35,1	49,0614	15,9202	0	ML	1,8	A	

2022-05-31 11:20:14,1	48,6118	15,7603	0	ML	1	A	
2022-06-01 07:58:48,7	49,3605	16,3586	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-06-02 07:29:22,6	49,0105	16,3344	0	ML	1,2	A	Olbramovice
2022-06-02 11:59:28,2	49,2685	16,6124	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-06-03 08:32:15,3	49,2628	16,9378	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-03 11:02:33,0	48,6181	15,8345	0	ML	0,7	A	
2022-06-06 08:15:26,4	48,8117	16,1626	0	ML	1,8	A	Hodonice
2022-06-07 08:16:44,3	49,4610	16,6038	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-08 08:03:39,7	48,9978	16,3564	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2022-06-08 08:27:45,0	49,2419	16,9207	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-09 08:02:17,8	48,8207	16,1501	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2022-06-10 08:12:49,0	49,7802	16,1789	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-06-10 12:55:23,6	48,5544	16,3261	0	ML	1	A	
2022-06-14 08:08:08,6	49,3095	16,8365	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-14 08:26:55,6	48,9490	18,2520	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-14 08:56:52,1	48,8562	15,5981	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-06-14 08:58:01,0	48,8548	15,5853	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-06-14 11:01:57,1	48,9659	15,8768	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-06-14 13:10:06,2	49,1973	16,1411	0	ML	1,4	A	Vícenice
2022-06-14 13:50:32,0	48,7207	15,8512	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-06-15 06:18:50,2	49,3150	16,5428	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-06-15 10:33:42,5	48,6069	15,8280	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-06-15 12:14:36,4	48,4190	17,2610	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-06-16 07:19:35,7	49,4126	16,0331	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-16 08:29:36,1	49,1325	16,5404	0	ML	1,7	A	Želešice
2022-06-17 07:30:08,0	49,2174	16,7711	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-17 08:26:13,2	49,3626	15,6245	0	ML	2	A	
2022-06-17 10:33:52,2	48,9443	15,6570	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-20 07:16:55,4	48,9998	16,3549	0	ML	1	A	Olbramovice
2022-06-21 09:08:51,5	49,1111	16,5733	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-06-21 12:11:32,4	48,9550	17,9190	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-06-22 08:34:14,6	49,2169	16,9645	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-22 10:58:12,1	48,6127	15,8517	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-06-23 07:12:43,9	49,2020	16,7422	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-24 08:57:47,4	48,5442	16,3179	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-06-27 08:04:51,0	49,2883	16,9314	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-27 09:13:16,1	49,6707	16,3359	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-28 07:38:04,3	49,0652	16,4566	0	ML	1	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-06-28 07:55:18,9	49,3303	17,1205	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-28 08:02:58,5	49,2420	16,9539	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-06-29 08:01:06,5	49,4536	16,5636	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-06-29 08:16:52,5	49,4785	16,1368	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-06-30 07:22:25,1	49,3814	16,0379	0	ML	2	A	
2022-06-30 08:40:31,0	49,2692	16,8908	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-06-30 10:00:24,7	48,1076	16,9283	0	ML	1,6	A	

2022-07-01 06:01:56,5	48,9908	16,3589	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-07-01 06:02:20,9	49,2318	16,7324	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-01 08:10:38,0	48,8398	15,5992	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-07-01 09:43:24,6	48,8482	15,5924	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-07-01 13:10:18,0	48,8532	15,5928	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-07-04 10:14:56,2	49,6641	16,3323	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-07-06 12:07:32,0	48,6198	15,8393	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-07-07 07:01:30,0	49,0767	16,4262	0	ML	1,6	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-07-09 02:07:43,5	48,1150	16,1010	7	ML	0,2	T	Alland
2022-07-11 08:00:42,0	48,8128	16,1655	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2022-07-11 08:30:26,9	48,1000	16,1170	6	ML	0,9	T	Alland
2022-07-12 08:00:17,4	48,9885	16,3606	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-07-12 08:48:35,1	49,2354	16,9474	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-07-12 11:19:17,6	48,6192	15,8484	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-07-12 11:19:32,8	48,6194	15,8171	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-07-13 07:03:37,6	49,2176	16,7729	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-13 08:31:19,8	49,3389	15,6027	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-14 07:14:23,1	48,8571	15,5891	0	ML	1	A	
2022-07-14 08:59:00,1	48,4358	17,2807	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-07-14 09:10:43,3	49,4710	16,6894	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-07-14 09:14:59,2	49,2917	16,7709	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-15 07:03:47,9	49,2202	16,7400	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-15 07:23:50,5	48,9914	16,3664	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-07-17 14:29:03,8	49,8540	17,1820	9	ML	0,4	T	Ruda
2022-07-18 08:36:29,6	49,2701	16,9297	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-07-18 08:51:47,8	49,2472	16,9038	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-07-18 09:04:29,5	49,3443	15,6275	0	ML	2	A	
2022-07-19 08:12:49,2	49,2028	16,3394	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-07-19 08:14:04,6	49,1949	16,3344	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-07-20 11:16:04,9	48,8511	15,5948	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-07-21 08:47:57,2	48,5612	16,3508	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-07-21 09:58:59,6	49,2111	16,1091	0	ML	1,3	A	Vícenice
2022-07-22 07:54:29,1	49,7738	17,8189	0	ML	2	A	
2022-07-24 04:06:04,0	49,6850	16,7060	14	ML	0,3	T	Městečko Trnávka
2022-07-25 08:03:58,0	48,8120	16,1669	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2022-07-27 06:59:28,3	48,4072	17,2553	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-07-27 08:33:51,8	48,8264	16,1398	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2022-07-27 10:56:21,1	48,8535	15,5937	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-07-28 08:32:29,0	49,4360	16,1544	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-07-29 08:25:41,7	49,2381	16,9196	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-07-29 09:20:07,6	49,2144	16,1219	0	ML	1,3	A	Vícenice
2022-07-29 09:52:38,1	49,5865	15,9508	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-08-01 08:11:57,0	49,1469	16,4972	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-08-01 08:52:03,6	48,8444	15,6137	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-08-01 12:58:37,2	49,2620	16,6257	0	ML	1,6	A	

2022-08-03 07:29:32,9	49,4436	16,6227	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-03 13:53:08,0	48,6051	15,8722	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-08-04 20:55:13,1	48,6700	15,8500	12	ML	1,2	T	Austria, Semmering
2022-08-05 07:01:19,3	49,2203	16,6939	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-08-05 07:52:38,0	48,7743	15,9116	0	ML	1	A	
2022-08-05 09:56:43,2	49,6284	16,7900	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-08-08 08:10:02,2	48,5295	17,4859	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-08-08 08:37:07,5	49,6030	15,9063	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-08-09 07:36:04,7	49,5165	16,0919	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-08-09 09:34:47,2	48,9895	16,3651	0	ML	1,4	A	Olbramovice
2022-08-09 10:21:57,1	48,9353	15,6566	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-10 07:40:39,3	48,8140	16,1533	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2022-08-10 09:14:42,8	49,1107	16,5544	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-08-11 07:36:31,8	49,2256	16,8912	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-08-15 07:32:57,0	49,3635	16,3920	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-08-15 07:54:20,0	49,1282	17,8789	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-08-15 08:28:37,0	48,5719	17,5379	0	ML	2	A	
2022-08-15 09:06:00,0	49,7909	16,1676	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-08-16 06:59:49,3	49,4384	16,5652	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-08-16 10:02:05,0	49,2817	16,4465	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-08-17 07:15:32,3	48,5281	17,4813	0	ML	2	A	
2022-08-17 08:41:53,8	49,3515	15,6148	0	ML	2	A	
2022-08-18 07:59:36,9	49,3760	16,3796	0	ML	2	A	
2022-08-18 08:33:26,1	49,2608	16,9293	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-08-18 08:34:42,5	49,2551	16,8777	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-19 07:13:18,7	48,9922	16,3538	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-08-22 08:15:17,0	49,3575	16,1271	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-08-22 08:35:12,1	49,1996	16,3275	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-08-22 09:20:10,2	49,6546	16,9968	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-08-23 07:48:03,2	49,0393	16,5050	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-08-23 08:00:05,0	49,3142	16,9636	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-23 08:39:01,7	49,2469	16,8541	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-08-24 08:20:56,2	49,2419	16,9688	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-08-24 09:06:38,5	48,8173	16,1458	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2022-08-25 07:01:00,3	49,0795	16,4584	0	ML	1,6	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-08-26 08:22:35,0	49,4517	16,6409	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-08-26 08:25:33,4	49,4516	16,6106	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-08-26 09:57:34,5	48,5554	16,2071	0	ML	1	A	
2022-08-30 08:59:12,9	49,2129	16,1234	0	ML	1,4	A	Vícenice
2022-08-31 07:16:27,4	49,2068	16,8495	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-31 07:57:54,2	49,3619	16,3714	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-08-31 14:56:45,7	49,5085	15,7165	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-09-02 08:26:43,3	49,2267	16,9239	0	ML	2	A	
2022-09-04 12:11:02,9	48,3370	16,7490	9	ML	0,4	T	Gänserndorf
2022-09-05 08:43:37,0	49,3379	16,3498	0	ML	1,6	A	

2022-09-06 07:48:49,4	49,5517	16,0683	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-06 08:21:27,8	49,2485	16,9311	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-09-06 11:53:45,5	48,6135	15,8468	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-09-06 11:59:50,0	49,2063	16,1172	0	ML	1,8	A	Vícenice
2022-09-07 07:30:02,0	49,2598	16,6952	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-09-08 08:19:27,6	49,4650	16,1274	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-09-08 10:00:56,8	49,2995	16,5636	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-09-09 09:45:04,4	48,4068	17,1735	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-09-10 00:06:55,1	49,7610	17,2950	16	ML	0,2	T	S od Šternberka, Chabičov
2022-09-12 08:11:17,4	49,3513	16,1255	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-09-12 08:23:58,7	49,2493	16,8891	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-09-12 10:51:26,1	48,9682	15,9113	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-09-12 12:14:50,4	49,1252	16,5283	0	ML	0,9	A	Želešice
2022-09-13 07:25:08,0	48,8159	16,1775	0	ML	1,3	A	Hodonice
2022-09-13 08:51:15,9	48,8410	18,3040	6	ML	0,9	T	Slatina nad Bebravou
2022-09-14 01:34:15,0	48,8494	18,2739	6	ML	0,8	T	Trenčianské Teplice
2022-09-14 03:01:31,5	48,8359	18,2624	9	ML	0,6	T	Trenčianské Teplice
2022-09-14 07:49:39,8	48,5651	17,4623	0	ML	2	A	
2022-09-14 09:01:54,1	49,6825	16,3468	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-09-15 08:02:55,7	49,1195	16,5565	0	ML	1,7	A	Želešice
2022-09-16 07:12:22,9	49,2083	16,7791	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-16 08:11:11,4	49,4550	16,5553	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-16 09:23:12,1	48,6102	15,8674	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-09-16 11:46:14,4	48,6114	15,8451	0	ML	0,7	A	
2022-09-19 07:58:17,0	49,3450	16,1294	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-19 08:34:59,2	49,2823	16,9402	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-20 07:49:00,0	49,3571	16,7648	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-09-20 08:28:01,2	48,8154	16,1541	0	ML	1,8	A	Hodonice
2022-09-20 11:20:14,5	48,6347	15,8211	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-09-20 11:29:12,1	49,5950	16,8290	15	ML	0,0	T	Konice
2022-09-22 08:09:00,8	49,2263	16,7898	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-09-22 09:06:52,5	49,6663	16,3549	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-23 10:43:09,6	49,2160	16,1053	0	ML	1,5	A	Vícenice
2022-09-26 07:23:36,8	49,4377	16,6117	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-26 07:31:35,3	49,3374	16,1301	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-09-29 07:56:34,5	48,6021	17,3750	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-09-29 08:20:45,9	49,3350	16,0400	0	ML	2,1	A	
2022-09-30 07:31:20,8	49,2094	16,6832	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-09-30 08:02:18,7	48,8182	16,1535	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2022-10-02 05:52:53,3	48,3200	16,8400	14	ML	2,9	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 06:28:10,0	48,3126	16,8458	14	ML	1,8	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 06:32:10,4	48,2862	16,8179	4	ML	0,6	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 08:17:35,1	48,3095	16,8420	14	ML	2,6	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 08:28:26,4	48,3272	16,8718	14	ML	2	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 08:34:04,4	48,2870	16,8680	14	ML	2,1	T	Gänserndorf

2022-10-02 08:41:32,3	48,3354	16,8643	14	ML	1,6	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 08:54:49,7	48,3251	16,8437	13	ML	1,2	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 09:10:08,8	48,3252	16,8717	14	ML	2	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 09:10:34,4	48,3062	16,8725	14	ML	2,3	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-02 11:45:33,1	48,4010	16,8790	5	ML	0,2	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:19:44,2	48,4020	16,8770	4	ML	0,3	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:20:00,8	48,4007	16,8788	5	ML	0,8	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:23:58,7	48,4011	16,8743	4	ML	0,7	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:25:21,5	48,4016	16,8787	5	ML	1,1	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:32:58,7	48,4020	16,8722	3	ML	1,6	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 12:54:19,2	48,4010	16,8790	5	ML	0,5	T	Suchohrad
2022-10-02 17:06:01,9	48,3027	16,8024	14	ML	1	T	Gänserndorf
2022-10-03 07:17:07,2	49,5583	16,0617	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-03 07:44:51,0	49,2150	16,7028	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-10-03 10:24:55,7	49,0627	15,9224	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-10-04 08:27:29,5	49,5564	17,0336	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-10-04 08:29:18,6	49,1933	16,8134	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-04 08:56:06,3	48,9766	16,3813	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-10-05 09:31:58,6	49,1107	16,5774	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2022-10-07 08:12:51,1	49,3467	15,6137	0	ML	2	A	
2022-10-10 07:52:32,0	49,2696	16,9143	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-10-10 08:59:51,0	49,6693	16,3576	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-10-11 08:00:10,2	49,4518	16,6360	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-10-11 09:30:01,1	48,4646	17,2433	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-10-11 10:47:54,9	49,6045	15,9081	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-11 20:02:55,0	48,3860	16,0300	10	ML	0,0	T	Tulln a.d. Donau
2022-10-12 08:06:54,2	49,0991	16,4162	0	ML	1,7	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-10-12 08:52:06,5	49,2941	16,3401	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-10-14 08:52:58,6	49,0153	16,3270	0	ML	1,4	A	Olbramovice
2022-10-17 07:45:14,5	49,4500	16,6228	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-10-18 08:00:46,0	49,0781	16,3725	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-10-18 10:01:44,8	49,2877	16,4740	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-10-19 08:14:13,3	49,3715	16,3821	0	ML	2	A	
2022-10-20 08:00:03,7	48,4471	17,2056	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-20 08:39:17,5	49,0756	16,4431	0	ML	1,3	A	Dolní Kounice
2022-10-20 11:09:18,0	48,6159	15,8448	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-10-24 08:30:09,3	49,2404	16,8948	0	ML	2	A	
2022-10-24 09:02:09,6	49,3402	15,6329	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-24 11:25:03,9	49,6379	16,7722	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-10-25 08:04:29,1	49,4540	16,5927	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-10-25 08:30:55,0	48,8451	15,5926	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-10-25 08:47:22,9	49,2090	16,7508	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-10-25 10:00:31,6	48,1411	16,8914	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-10-25 10:46:25,3	49,6628	17,0076	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-26 09:00:56,4	49,3271	17,1249	0	ML	1,9	A	

2022-10-27 08:38:53,6	49,2286	16,9925	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-10-28 03:49:53,9	48,5605	17,4883	9	ML	1,2	T	Dobrá Voda
2022-10-28 10:40:56,7	48,4260	17,1949	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-10-31 05:08:29,9	49,9610	17,8860	14	ML	0,1	T	Opava
2022-10-31 09:31:04,1	49,3347	16,3681	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-11-01 08:34:09,3	49,2614	16,9905	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-11-01 08:47:32,1	49,4268	16,0237	0	ML	2	A	
2022-11-01 09:54:45,9	49,7204	17,7942	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-11-02 08:29:10,4	49,3513	16,3499	0	ML	2	A	
2022-11-03 03:46:43,4	48,5480	17,7023	14	ML	1,3	T	Vrbové
2022-11-07 07:36:38,9	49,2828	16,5757	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-11-07 09:55:43,1	49,0097	16,3466	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2022-11-08 00:33:35,3	49,3270	17,3620	18	ML	0,3	T	Kroměříž
2022-11-08 00:33:47,8	49,3330	17,3560	19	ML	0,1	T	Kroměříž
2022-11-08 08:04:40,6	49,4485	16,6134	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-11-08 09:24:27,0	49,4649	16,1552	0	ML	1,9	A	
2022-11-08 09:33:53,4	48,6193	15,8514	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-11-14 08:10:50,2	49,3511	16,1294	0	ML	1,6	A	
2022-11-14 09:23:37,8	49,3783	16,3863	0	ML	2	A	
2022-11-14 23:04:20,6	49,9390	17,9820	14	ML	0,2	T	V od Opavy, Velké Hoštice
2022-11-15 09:04:15,8	48,8148	16,1768	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2022-11-15 10:18:14,4	49,1220	16,5509	0	ML	1,7	A	Želešice
2022-11-15 10:25:38,7	48,6159	15,7497	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-11-15 14:16:18,7	48,6175	15,7448	0	ML	0,9	A	
2022-11-16 09:30:52,2	49,0068	16,3454	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2022-11-16 10:10:15,1	49,3769	16,3826	0	ML	2	A	
2022-11-18 10:57:06,6	48,6176	15,8334	0	ML	1	A	
2022-11-21 09:34:42,7	48,8151	16,1488	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2022-11-21 09:41:42,5	49,2242	16,8950	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-11-22 08:23:18,5	49,2310	16,7238	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-11-22 10:28:42,0	49,2974	16,3604	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-11-22 11:05:46,3	49,4561	16,6313	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-11-25 08:55:46,2	49,1924	16,3383	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-11-25 09:16:15,0	49,4443	16,1357	0	ML	2	A	
2022-11-25 09:21:45,8	48,5800	17,4420	8	ML	0,4	T	Jablonica
2022-11-26 07:58:58,1	48,5470	17,4420	7	ML	0,7	T	Trstín
2022-11-28 09:25:31,8	49,4499	16,6186	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-11-28 10:15:53,4	48,8519	15,6014	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-11-28 11:13:03,6	49,0623	15,9078	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-11-29 08:46:47,6	48,7791	15,9133	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-11-29 10:12:13,6	49,8265	17,0972	0	ML	1,7	A	
2022-12-06 09:33:02,4	49,4511	16,6189	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-12-08 08:45:20,1	48,9991	16,3469	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2022-12-09 10:24:38,1	49,2992	16,2436	0	ML	2	A	
2022-12-09 14:21:37,5	48,9631	15,7034	0	ML	1,1	A	

2022-12-09 18:58:42,0	49,7950	17,3670	9	ML	0,0	T	Z od Mor. Berouna, Krahulčí
2022-12-12 09:13:27,3	49,2879	16,5663	0	ML	1,4	A	
2022-12-12 11:56:13,8	48,6143	15,8464	0	ML	1,2	A	
2022-12-12 13:17:14,0	49,2002	16,1210	0	ML	1,4	A	Vícenice
2022-12-13 00:18:06,7	49,2402	17,4848	15	ML	0,5	T	Otrokovice
2022-12-13 08:33:53,0	49,2077	16,7600	0	ML	1,5	A	
2022-12-13 09:08:59,2	48,5771	17,3963	0	ML	1,8	A	
2022-12-13 10:03:05,4	48,8562	15,5914	0	ML	1,3	A	
2022-12-13 23:54:40,2	48,8552	17,9752	4	ML	0,6	T	Trenčín
2022-12-14 11:12:47,2	48,8535	15,5915	0	ML	1,1	A	
2022-12-19 09:38:13,1	49,2208	16,7337	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-01-09 08:00:14,4	48,4768	16,3899	0	ML	0,8	A	
2023-01-09 09:27:09,2	48,9990	16,3531	0	ML	1,2	A	Olbramovice
2023-01-12 17:10:39,6	49,7600	17,2270	13	ML	0,2	T	SZ od Šternberka, Mladějovice
2023-01-20 19:13:08,9	49,7380	17,6110	16	ML	0,2	T	Budišov nad Budišovkou
2023-01-20 19:22:52,2	49,7402	17,6068	16	ML	0,7	T	Budišov nad Budišovkou
2023-01-20 19:47:51,4	49,7380	17,6110	16	ML	0,2	T	Budišov nad Budišovkou
2023-01-20 23:35:56,9	49,7380	17,6120	16	ML	0,2	T	Budišov nad Budišovkou
2023-01-23 12:37:53,8	49,3722	16,3948	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-01-24 08:04:27,8	49,2124	16,6522	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-01-27 09:51:32,8	49,2999	16,2305	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-01-31 08:12:30,1	49,3593	16,1279	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-02-03 03:13:51,5	48,6500	17,5700	0	ML	0,8	A	Brezová pod Bradlom
2023-02-04 09:33:37,2	48,2090	15,5460	6	ML	1,0	T	St. Pölten
2023-02-07 21:18:25,7	49,2103	17,3884	12	ML	0,6	T	Kostelany
2023-02-08 12:11:44,2	48,6221	15,8351	0	ML	0,8	A	
2023-02-10 10:00:05,5	48,4377	17,2306	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-02-20 10:59:00,4	49,1122	16,5564	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2023-02-20 19:51:29,0	48,1900	16,0420	4	ML	0,6	T	Pressbaum
2023-02-21 09:35:39,1	48,8243	16,1330	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2023-02-21 10:59:02,8	49,3114	17,1357	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-02-24 08:30:14,0	49,2259	16,6906	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-02-27 10:48:04,7	49,2624	16,9752	0	ML	2	A	
2023-02-27 11:05:07,6	49,3017	16,2471	0	ML	1,3	A	
2023-03-02 12:58:48,1	48,6111	15,8411	0	ML	0,9	A	
2023-03-06 08:46:50,9	49,5496	16,0770	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-03-06 09:18:42,2	49,1142	16,5630	0	ML	1,5	A	Želešice
2023-03-08 10:53:04,3	48,6087	15,8725	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-03-10 08:24:46,8	49,2276	16,7357	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-03-10 09:37:37,7	48,8589	15,5826	0	ML	1,3	A	
2023-03-10 10:01:10,3	49,7809	16,1955	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-03-13 08:48:25,8	49,0762	16,4663	0	ML	1,4	A	Dolní Kounice
2023-03-20 11:24:50,6	48,6073	15,8320	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-03-21 09:45:12,9	49,0154	16,3468	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2023-03-24 08:21:14,3	49,3504	16,1324	0	ML	1,6	A	

2023-03-24 08:38:58,5	49,2106	16,7709	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-03-24 09:30:32,5	49,3647	16,3919	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-03-26 11:45:25,3	48,4229	17,4105	7	ML	0,8	T	Dolany
2023-03-26 18:32:39,0	49,4170	17,9750	23	ML	0,4	T	J od Val. Meziříčí, Bystřička
2023-03-27 07:39:32,6	49,4882	16,6101	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-03-27 11:33:29,7	48,9369	15,6475	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-03-28 08:31:14,7	49,4604	16,1181	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-03-29 09:27:32,6	48,8115	16,1602	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2023-03-29 12:43:19,0	48,6158	15,8341	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-03-30 11:39:07,5	49,3605	17,0767	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-03-31 10:10:02,5	48,8551	15,5856	0	ML	1,3	A	
2023-04-03 08:30:28,9	48,8173	16,1500	0	ML	1,7	A	Hodonice
2023-04-04 07:49:45,5	49,3609	15,6130	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-04-07 20:30:13,7	48,3678	17,1254	6	ML	1,2	T	Pernek
2023-04-11 07:24:21,0	49,2294	16,7057	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-04-12 18:03:21,1	48,5923	17,4168	6	ML	0,5	T	Jablonica
2023-04-13 22:33:32,5	48,6171	17,7473	11	ML	0,7	T	Vrbové
2023-04-14 07:59:34,4	49,5186	17,6677	0	ML	2,1	A	
2023-04-17 07:57:43,9	49,0028	16,3664	0	ML	1	A	Olbramovice
2023-04-19 09:08:13,0	48,6083	15,8495	0	ML	1	A	
2023-04-19 11:20:21,6	49,6686	16,9833	0	ML	2,2	A	
2023-04-21 07:04:10,3	48,5269	17,4645	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-04-21 07:34:34,9	48,3996	17,2905	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-04-21 10:00:26,3	48,1420	16,8892	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-04-24 00:23:59,7	49,2450	17,1380	20	ML	0,3	T	Morkovice-Slížany
2023-04-24 11:10:16,6	49,2226	16,1194	0	ML	1,2	A	Vícenice
2023-04-26 12:22:06,0	48,6155	15,8538	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-04-28 06:03:24,2	48,3750	17,2328	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-02 07:51:21,8	49,4221	16,0313	0	ML	2,1	A	
2023-05-03 07:16:13,0	49,1996	16,7502	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-05-03 09:00:50,0	48,8243	16,1484	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2023-05-03 15:08:42,0	48,5365	17,6823	1	ML	0,8	T	Nižná
2023-05-04 08:28:30,8	49,2536	16,8934	0	ML	2,1	A	
2023-05-05 06:44:04,9	49,2325	16,6166	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-05-05 07:05:52,3	49,4252	16,0281	0	ML	2	A	
2023-05-05 07:34:02,3	48,5168	17,4785	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-09 10:32:10,0	48,9456	15,6596	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-05-10 07:33:19,9	49,2464	16,6828	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-10 08:17:10,2	48,8095	16,1251	0	ML	1,5	A	Hodonice
2023-05-10 10:03:35,5	49,0594	15,9169	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-05-11 09:08:35,1	49,3614	15,6114	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-05-12 06:55:55,9	48,4329	17,2144	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-15 10:23:45,4	49,3421	17,1187	0	ML	2	A	
2023-05-16 08:49:44,7	49,1478	16,5102	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2023-05-17 08:00:45,7	49,7933	16,1753	0	ML	1,6	A	

2023-05-18 03:32:12,7	49,9980	17,3870	10	ML	0,1	T	Bruntál
2023-05-18 07:13:03,0	49,0872	16,4472	0	ML	1,4	A	Dolní Kounice
2023-05-18 09:19:59,6	48,4123	17,2279	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-05-19 08:07:06,3	48,9922	16,3594	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2023-05-19 10:44:23,8	49,6402	16,7622	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-22 08:50:10,0	49,2328	16,8751	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-22 10:22:26,0	48,6090	15,8548	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-05-23 08:02:48,7	49,0283	16,3418	0	ML	1,2	A	
2023-05-26 07:30:53,7	49,4502	16,5928	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-05-26 08:24:33,9	49,2217	16,9288	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-29 07:16:08,9	49,2158	16,6914	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-05-29 07:50:06,5	49,6983	17,7785	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-29 08:32:39,2	49,7092	17,3341	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-29 08:39:29,3	49,3764	15,6238	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-29 08:56:29,0	49,6675	16,3341	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-05-30 02:03:24,8	49,9050	15,6130	11	ML	0,5	T	Prachovice
2023-05-30 07:24:08,0	49,5428	16,0572	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-05-30 12:59:55,7	48,8519	15,6034	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-05-31 06:32:22,8	49,2473	16,7740	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-05-31 07:19:40,5	49,3204	16,1277	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-06-02 08:43:14,8	49,4687	16,1466	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-06-03 19:57:12,0	48,5043	17,3222	9	ML	0,6	T	Plavecký Mikuláš
2023-06-06 06:00:15,7	48,4195	17,2407	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-06-06 08:16:01,8	49,3461	17,0505	0	ML	2,1	A	
2023-06-06 08:36:48,8	49,2895	16,8769	0	ML	2	A	
2023-06-06 09:59:59,2	48,1716	16,8846	0	ML	1,2	A	
2023-06-07 06:22:41,7	49,4184	16,7980	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-06-07 08:32:57,9	49,3399	16,3662	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-06-07 11:29:01,5	48,6186	15,8400	0	ML	1	A	
2023-06-08 08:00:57,6	48,9907	16,3520	0	ML	1,7	A	Olbramovice
2023-06-09 06:03:47,0	49,2430	16,7183	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-06-12 07:35:18,9	49,2043	16,3398	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-06-12 07:42:29,8	49,3144	16,1472	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-06-12 10:00:03,3	49,1826	16,1290	0	ML	1,2	A	Vícenice
2023-06-13 07:46:00,9	49,0141	16,3355	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2023-06-13 08:24:56,2	49,3536	17,0831	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-06-13 08:26:01,6	49,3553	16,3750	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-06-14 08:07:20,1	49,4579	16,1502	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-06-16 07:46:54,0	49,4312	16,0366	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-06-19 10:00:04,0	48,1426	16,9271	0	ML	1,2	A	
2023-06-20 08:50:01,0	49,1348	16,5565	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2023-06-20 10:01:34,8	49,3103	16,4664	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-06-20 11:50:05,7	48,9430	15,6466	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-06-20 12:08:00,0	48,9516	15,9035	0	ML	1	A	
2023-06-21 07:25:21,5	49,4302	16,5874	0	ML	1,8	A	

2023-06-22 06:09:13,5	49,8640	17,1940	10	ML	0,1	T	JZ od Rýmařova, Ruda
2023-06-26 08:38:42,8	49,2566	16,9503	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-06-27 08:48:10,4	49,1204	16,5528	0	ML	1,5	A	Želešice
2023-06-27 09:42:52,0	48,6088	15,8553	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-06-28 10:24:17,1	49,3502	16,3913	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-07-04 08:29:39,1	48,4628	17,3452	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-07-07 07:44:33,7	48,7251	15,8560	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-07-10 08:21:21,6	49,4524	16,1583	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-07-11 07:41:27,3	49,3785	15,6267	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-07-12 07:06:41,8	48,4635	17,5828	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-07-12 07:50:46,8	49,2094	16,7988	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-07-13 07:29:45,5	49,2468	17,2027	0	ML	2,3	A	
2023-07-13 07:51:38,3	49,3258	16,7432	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-07-14 08:24:34,2	49,1979	16,3299	0	ML	0,8	A	
2023-07-17 07:08:14,6	49,1168	16,5649	0	ML	0,8	A	Želešice
2023-07-17 08:37:31,1	48,4091	17,3103	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-07-17 08:57:24,2	48,8246	16,1399	0	ML	1,6	A	Hodonice
2023-07-17 11:25:35,4	49,2250	16,1207	0	ML	1,7	A	Vícenice
2023-07-18 07:22:31,3	49,2155	16,7329	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-07-18 09:45:33,7	48,3946	17,1907	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-07-19 10:04:04,5	48,6149	15,8457	0	ML	1,3	A	
2023-07-19 10:05:30,2	48,6205	15,8211	0	ML	0,9	A	
2023-07-20 05:59:56,6	49,3408	16,8429	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-07-20 07:36:14,0	49,5164	16,1194	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-07-21 06:04:12,9	48,7993	16,1985	0	ML	0,5	A	Hodonice
2023-07-21 06:51:27,6	48,8418	15,5905	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-07-24 05:28:55,5	48,4735	17,4125	5	ML	0,6	T	Horné Orešany
2023-07-24 07:45:20,2	49,0580	16,4483	0	ML	1,2	A	Dolní Kounice
2023-07-24 08:34:33,2	49,3341	16,4049	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-07-25 09:04:44,1	49,6817	16,4259	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-07-26 08:35:47,9	48,4642	17,5035	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-07-27 11:58:50,9	48,6083	15,8446	0	ML	1,1	A	
2023-07-28 08:00:53,8	48,9933	16,3517	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2023-07-28 08:25:49,9	49,2085	16,7738	0	ML	1,6	A	
2023-07-31 05:34:52,6	49,7690	16,6280	21	ML	0,2	T	Moravská Třebová
2023-07-31 08:57:36,7	49,1184	16,5846	0	ML	1,6	A	Želešice
2023-08-01 08:31:28,1	49,2543	16,9147	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-01 09:17:55,0	48,4283	17,2026	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-08-03 11:08:17,2	48,6123	15,8447	0	ML	1,2	A	
2023-08-08 07:31:40,5	49,4383	16,0278	0	ML	2	A	
2023-08-08 10:16:50,5	49,2467	16,7328	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-08 10:22:13,3	49,3716	16,3949	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-09 10:01:41,3	49,3210	16,4805	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-09 10:11:10,9	48,6012	15,8552	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-08-10 00:01:27,8	48,1630	16,6760	6	ML	1,9	T	Orth an der Donau

2023-08-10 08:27:38,6	49,2184	16,9623	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-11 09:02:47,9	49,3026	16,3479	0	ML	1,7	A	
2023-08-11 16:23:21,2	48,7249	15,8276	0	ML	1,2	A	
2023-08-14 07:21:08,5	49,2092	16,7229	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-08-14 12:34:08,2	49,2191	16,1254	0	ML	1,4	A	Vícenice
2023-08-15 07:16:43,2	49,2155	16,7569	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-08-16 06:23:03,9	48,4087	17,2541	0	ML	1,5	A	
2023-08-17 10:14:22,9	48,4279	17,2634	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-18 08:03:02,5	48,9962	16,3656	0	ML	1,5	A	Olbramovice
2023-08-18 08:44:45,4	48,8545	15,5890	0	ML	1,4	A	
2023-08-23 07:53:46,5	49,0199	16,3252	0	ML	1,6	A	Olbramovice
2023-08-23 08:40:19,2	49,3597	15,6187	0	ML	2	A	
2023-08-24 04:24:34,3	49,4296	17,4224	21	ML	1	T	Přerov
2023-08-29 07:19:46,1	49,5385	16,0568	0	ML	1,8	A	
2023-08-29 09:59:28,9	49,3619	17,1003	0	ML	2	A	
2023-08-30 08:09:40,5	48,8462	16,1238	0	ML	1,2	A	Hodonice
2023-08-30 09:17:11,7	49,4447	16,6026	0	ML	1,9	A	
2023-08-30 11:16:25,5	48,6066	15,8663	0	ML	1	A	
2023-08-31 10:00:03,8	48,5395	17,4810	0	ML	1,7	A	

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a € 2.32 mil. grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

T A

Č R
